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European Polar Research Area**

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First progress report on dissemination activities

Submission of Deliverable

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The first Progress Report on Dissemination activities (Deliverable 5.4) of EU-PolarNet 2 – due on October 31, 2021 – was compiled by UNIVIE/APRI with the support of all EU-PolarNet 2 partners. It comprises all dissemination activities of EU-PolarNet 2 in its first year, from project kick-off in October 2020 until October 31, 2021. The content covers dissemination activities at conferences and events (section 2), webinars (section 3), online outreach via the webpage, newsletter, and social media channels (section 4), and the communication pack (section 5). More detailed information about events, along with screenshots and images can be found in the Annex (section 6).

1 Introduction

Corporate and external communication is a key task within EU-PolarNet 2's Work Package (WP) 5. The communication activities listed in the following sections describe the strategic and targeted measures with which the work of EU-PolarNet 2 and its results and outcomes are promoted to a wide range of audiences. These measures comprise dissemination activities at conferences and events (section 2), webinars (section 3), online outreach via the webpage, newsletter, and social media channels (section 4), and a communication pack to provide outreach materials to partners (section 5).

2 Dissemination at conferences and events

EU-PolarNet 2 consortium members have actively promoted the work of the project at 14 national, European and international conferences and workshops during the past 12 months. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and related restrictions on travelling and in-person meetings, the majority of these events was organised online. This prevented the on-site distribution of promotional material. However, online material gained importance (see sections 4 and 5).

The table below lists the past 12 months dissemination activities at meetings and events. More detailed information about these activities can be found in Annex 6.1.

Name of event	Date	Location	Activity	Representative/s
Visit of Finland's Arctic and Antarctic Ambassador Petteri Vuorimäki and his team at Ministry of Foreign Affairs Finland	06/10/2020	University of Oulu, Finland	Presentation	Kirsi Latola
EU Polar Science Week – EU-PolarNet 2 Kick-Off meeting	26/10/2020	Online	Plenary lecture, Chaining sessions, Session organisation	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel, Renuka Badhe, Joseph Nolan
EU Polar Science Week – EU-PolarNet 2 General Assembly	26/10/2020	Online	General assembly, closed session for EU-PolarNet 2 partners	All WP (co-)leaders,
EU Polar Science Week – EU Polar Cluster Annual Meeting	27/10/2020	Online	Presentation	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel
All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum	03/12/2020	Online	Presentation	Nicole Biebow
PPP-SERA Workshop – Co-production in the European Arctic weather, water, ice and climate services.	25/01/2021	Online	Presentation	Annette Scheepstra
Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) 2021	20-26/03/2021	Online	Conference attendance	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel
EU-PolarNet2: Norwegian Network Meeting	22/03/2021	Online	Kickoff-Meeting, Establishment of a Norwegian Expert Network for EU-PolarNet2	Representatives of Norwegian research institutions and the Research Council of Norway
ASSW21 workshop on Co-creating Arctic research with Indigenous communities	23/03/2021	Online	Participation, Presentation	Annette Scheepstra, Gertrude Saxinger,
UArctic Conference	17/05/2021	Online	Presentation	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel
All-Atlantic 2021 side event: Networking from pole to pole: facilitating access for research and infrastructure	03/06/2021	Online	Presentation, charring session	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel, Renuka Badhe, J Nolan, P Elshout
ICASS X Conference	19/06/2021	Online	Session organisation, presentation	Nicole Biebow, Peter Schweitzer, Annette

Session 'Co-creation of knowledge and co-design in Arctic research projects: re-thinking calls, seed money and evaluation criteria of funding organisations' Session 'An Integrated European Research Programme – Opportunities for Social Sciences and Humanities researchers in future EU research projects'				Scheepstra, Anneli Strobel, Gertrude Saxinger, Renuka Badhe
ESA Polar Science Cluster 2021	15-17/09/2021	Online	Presentation	Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel
EU H2020 project CHARTER General Assembly	05/10/2021	Online	Presentation	Kirsi Latola

3 Webinars

EU-PolarNet 2 supports information sharing and interaction of European Polar researchers with thematic webinars on topics of importance for the whole community.

More detailed information about the webinars can be found in Annex 6.2.

Name of webinar	Date	Organiser/Chair/Presenter	Attendees
EU Polar Cluster meeting in COVID-19 impacts for the cluster projects	15/01/2021	Pjotr Elshout, Elaina Ford, Anneli Strobel	40
European Perspectives on the Arctic Science Ministerial Process	28/04/2021	Renuka Badhe, Joseph Nolan, Pjotr Elshout, Nicole Biebow, Anneli Strobel	
How to apply for an EU PolarNet 2 Service Contract	08/07/2021	Nicole Biebow	48
Upcoming: The new EU Arctic policy and its contribution to Research and Innovation	24/11/2021 (TBC)	EU-PolarNet 2, EU Polar Cluster, European Polar Board	

4 Online outreach

4.1 Webpage

The EU-PolarNet 2 webpage is the main online dissemination platform for raising awareness about the project, sharing information related to the work of the consortium or affiliated projects and cooperation partners, and promoting upcoming events. The targeted audience ranges from the general public, to national and international policy makers, representatives from the industry, NGOs, interest groups and the wider science community. To meet the interest and needs of the various audience segments, the website offers both a wide range of informational static content and regularly updated contents, such as announcements and news.

The implementation of EU-PolarNet 2 website was one of the deliverables (D5.1.) of the *WP5 - Policy Advice, Dissemination, Communication - Providing evidence-based policy advice*. This deliverable was presented on 17th December 2020 by the IGOT-UL team with the support of the AWI team. In what concerns to the construction, the website (eu-polarnet.eu) was structured inside the Wordpress system and allocated to a domain provided by the company Domínios.pt. inside the Wordpress system. A set of plugins were installed with the aim of improving the aesthetic appearance, strengthen security, facilitate navigation, organise the databases and establish a private area for internal communication. Detailed information about webpage structure and statistics can be found in Annex 6.2

4.2 Newsletter

Quarterly newsletters are installed to distribute news from the consortium and affiliated projects, consortium partners, highlights in polar research and the EU Polar Cluster via Email. The newsletters aim to provide information on the European polar research community and to give a glimpse on activities and events coming up in the near future. Interested parties can register to receive the newsletter at the webpage (<https://eu-polarnet.eu/newsletter/>). Currently the newsletter has 854 recipients.

4.2.1 Newsletter 1

The first of the quarterly EU-PolarNet 2 newsletters of was written by the Management Support Team and distributed February 18, 2021.

Content:

- From EU-PolarNet 1 to EU-PolarNet 2
- Greetings from the EU-PolarNet 2 Management Support Team
- First EU Polar Science Week 2020
- EU-PolarNet 2 General Assembly
- EU Polar Cluster annual meeting at EU Polar Science Week
- Survey on stakeholder engagement
- EU Polar Cluster News
- Upcoming events

4.2.2 Newsletter 2

The second newsletter was written by the IGOT team and distributed May 7, 2021.

Content:

- News from EU-PolarNet 2
- EU Polar Cluster News
- Arctic Science Summit Week 2021
- Highlights in polar research
- An overview about the European expertise in Polar Research:
 - European Polar Board
 - Austrian Polar Research Institute (APRI)
 - Belgian Polar Research
 - Institute of Polar Sciences and Italian research (CNR)
 - University of Oulu & Thule Institute
 - Turkish Polar Research Institute
- Upcoming events

4.2.3 Newsletter 3

The third newsletter was written by the IGOT team and distributed July 30, 2021.

Content:

- News from EU-PolarNet 2
- EU-PolarNet 2 Call for Services
- All-Atlantic2021 side event on Polar Research
- ICASS X Panel on Co-creation of knowledge and co-design in Arctic research projects: rethinking calls, seed money and evaluation criteria of funding organisations
- First European Polar Science Week report is now available!
- Contribute now to our survey on 'Polar Observing Assets'
- EU Polar Cluster News
- Partner highlights on polar research
- An overview about the EU-PolarNet 2 partners expertise in Polar Research:
 - The Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP)
 - French Polar Research
 - The Spanish Polar community
 - The Centre for Polar Studies lead by the University of Silesia in Katowice, Poland
- Other news
- Upcoming events

4.3 Social media

The main objective of the social media channels is firstly to engage with the wider science community and stakeholders on a regular and immediate basis. Secondly, the channels allow consortium members to post and tweet content, while the YouTube channel features interviews with the members – thereby giving EU-PolarNet 2 a face.

EU-PolarNet 2 is present on social media with several accounts (Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube and LinkedIn). The Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn accounts are managed through the Crowdfire platform (<https://www.crowdfireapp.com>). This platform allows the creation and scheduling of publications made simultaneously on different channels and the creation of quarterly reports with the analytics of the social media accounts.

4.3.1 Twitter

The Twitter channel can be accessed at <https://twitter.com/eupolarnet>. At the time the EU-PolarNet channel has 2312 followers (by 27.09.2021).

4.3.2 Instagram

EU-PolarNet's instagram account can be accessed at <https://www.instagram.com/eupolarnet/>. At the time the account has 436 subscribers (by 27.09.2021).

4.3.3 Facebook

EU-PolarNet's facebook page can be accessed at <https://www.facebook.com/groups/1442027029433733/?ref=bookmarks>. To date the group has 1945 members (by 27.09.2021).

4.3.4 LinkedIn

EU-PolarNet's LinkedIn page can be accessed at <https://www.linkedin.com/in/eu-polarnet-3a21bb207/>. Currently the group has 98 members (by 27.09.2021).

4.3.5 YouTube

EU-PolarNet's YouTube channel can be accessed at <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqEzHkh6Q-ucxOFtd7UWHDA/featured>. At the time 32 videos are available and the channel has 67 subscribers (by 13.10.2021). Recordings of some events organised jointly with the EPB are also available on the EPB's YouTube channel (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCBZM37I_50Hb0g2AYcgqAsg/feature).

5 Outreach materials

To ensure a clear, strong and targeted dissemination and communication of EU-PolarNet 2 activities, a communication package was created (Deliverable No. D5.2).

5.1 Communication package

The EU-PolarNet2 communication package (Deliverable No. D5.2) includes presentation and poster templates and logos for project partners, along material for project dissemination (folder draft, factsheet draft). In addition, ideas for “giveaways” are listed. An overview of the project webpage (www.eu-polarnet.eu) and the social media channels (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn) is included. The communication package can be accessed via the EU-PolarNet 2 webpage at <https://eu-polarnet.eu/docs/d5-2-eu-polarnet-2-communication-package/>. The final folder and factsheet are included in annex 6.3 and 6.4.

6 Annexes

6.1 Details about dissemination activities at events

Type of activity	Presentation
Name of the event (in English)	Visit of Finland's Arctic and Antarctic Ambassador Petteri Vuorimäki and his team at Ministry of Foreign Affairs Finland
Date	06/10/2020
Venue	University of Oulu, Finland
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	oral presentation with slides
Link to event website if available	NA
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	sharing information about EU-PolarNet to Finnish Arctic and Antarctic Ambassador, discussion on European polar research and linkages to other relevant Polar policies and research
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Kirsi Latola, WP 2 leader of EU-PolarNet 2
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	Infrastructure catalogue from EU-PolarNet 1, EPRP
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	NA
Type and size of audience	policy makers and University leaders and Arctic researchers, approx. 10 persons
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Conference
Name of the event (in English)	EU Polar Science Week – EU-PolarNet 2 Kick-Off meeting, public session
Date	26/10/2020
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation/Plenary Lecture
Link to event website if available	https://eo4polar.esa.int/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	Co-organisers of conference, plenary lecture
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (presenter) Anneli Strobel (participant)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	Presentation

Images (Annex images and include credit information)	<p>Michael Mann (EU Arctic Ambassador) and Nicole Biebow</p>
Type and size of audience	Scientists, politicians, about 340
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Conference meeting
Name of the event (in English)	EU Polar Science Week – EU-PolarNet 2 Kick-Off meeting
Date	26/10/2020
Venue	Virtual
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentations
Link to event website if available	http://eo4polar.esa.int/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (AWI): plenary lecture Renuka Badhe (EPB): plenary lecture, chair of session, session organisation Joseph Nolan (EPB): plenary lecture, session organisation
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	Recorded sessions can be accessed online: https://livestream.com/esa/events/9362838
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	>350 participants Representatives from all EU-PolarNet 2 partner organisations.
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	General Assembly
Name of the event (in English)	EU Polar Science Week – EU-PolarNet 2 General Assembly, closed session by invitation only
Date	26/10/2020
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	WP presentation
Link to event website if available	

Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	All WP (co-)leaders, Management Support Team
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	Presentation
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	<p>Participants of first virtual EU-PolarNet 2 General Assembly</p>
Type and size of audience	EU-PolarNet 2 partners, 90
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Conference
Name of the event (in English)	EU Polar Science Week – EU Polar Cluster Annual Meeting, closed part
Date	27/10/2020
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation
Link to event website if available	
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	Introducing the new EU Polar Cluster, coordinated by EU-PolarNet 2. Minutes of meeting were Deliverable of the project.
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (presenter) Anneli Strobel (participant)

EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	Presentation
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	Scientists, 50
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Congress
Name of the event (in English)	All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum
Date	03/12/2020
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation
Link to event website if available	
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (presenter)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	<p>Why are the poles important for the Atlantic Ocean</p> <p>Why are the poles important for the Atlantic Ocean</p> <p>All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum FROM POLE TO POLE 3 - 4 December 2020 #AtlanticAll</p> <p>(Image: L. Sangalini, University of Bremen)</p> <p>(IPCC Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate)</p>
	Nicole Biebow explaining why the poles are important for the Atlantic Ocean @ All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum
Type and size of audience	Policy makers, research leaders, academics, civil society representatives, entrepreneurs
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Workshop
Name of the event (in English)	PPP-SERA Workshop – Co-production in the European Arctic weather, water, ice and climate services.
Date	25/01/2021
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation
Link to event website if available	https://salienseas.com/?p=3049

Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	Bringing together an interdisciplinary group of researchers involved in the co-production of weather, water, ice and climate (WWIC) information services, this online workshop aims to capture the state of the art of co-production approaches in European Arctic research.
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Annette Scheepstra (presenter)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet sciences White papers and the EU-PolarNet stakeholder whitepaper
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	Not applicable
Type and size of audience	About 40 participants interdisciplinary
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Conference
Name of the event (in English)	Arctic Science Summit Week 2021
Date	20 – 26/03/2021
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Attendance
Link to event website if available	https://assw2021.pt/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	Regular participation
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	N. Biebow, A. Strobel
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	500
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Establishment of a Norwegian Expert Network for EU-PolarNet2
Name of the event (in English)	EU-PolarNet2: Norwegian Network Meeting, Kickoff
Date	22/03/2021
Venue	Virtual – Zoom-meeting
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation of Work Programme, Norwegian contribution to deliverables and meetings, discussion and sharing of responsibilities.
Link to event website if available	
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	According to the contract a number of Norwegian research institutes will support RCN in fulfilling the work. These were first identified as 3 rd parties providing in-kind contribution. Their contribution will be provided under "service contracts".
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Representatives of the following institutions, according to cooperation agreement with the Research Council of Norway (RCN), participated: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Norwegian Polar Institute (NP). - Arctic University of Norway (UiT). - Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Institute (NERSC). - University of Bergen (UiB).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Institute of Marine Research (IMR). - Akvaplan-NIVA (APN). - GRID-Arendal (GridA). - Meteorological Institute of Norway (MET) - Western Reserach Institute (Vestforsk) - University of Oslo (UiO) - Norwegian institute of Air Research (NILU) - Northern Research Centre (NORCE) - Nord University (NORD) - Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) - University in Svalbard (UNIS).
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	Work Programme, Cooperation Agreement, Power point presentation
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	16 persons, representatives of Norwegian research institutions and the Research Council of Norway as partner in EU-PolarNet2.
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Workshop
Name of the event (in English)	ASSW21 workshop on Co-creating Arctic research with Indigenous communities
Date	23/03/2021
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation and organisation
Link to event website if available	https://iasc.info/news/iasc-news/775-activity-report-co-creating-arctic-research-together-with-indigenous-rightsholders-arctic-science-summit-week-assw21
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	The aim of the workshop was to contribute to recommendations for co-creating research projects with a focus on indigenous inclusion. The workshop is embedded in other activities like writing research notes, invite researchers and stake- and rightsholders to write down their experiences in order to create broad and lively discussions leading towards useful recommendations to improve successful co-created research projects.
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Annette Scheepstra (presenter and co-organiser), Gertrude Saxinger (presenter and co-organiser)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	Online: EU-PolarNet sciences White papers and the Integrated EU Polar Research Programme
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	Arctic scientists and Indigenous rightsholders, about 105 in total
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Conference
Name of the event (in English)	UArctic: session "European Cooperation in Polar Research - Past, Present and Future (European Polar Board 25th Anniversary), presentation: Polar research and European policy
Date	17/05/2021
Venue	online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation

Link to event website if available	https://www.uarctic.org/news/2021/4/webinar-european-perspectives-on-the-arctic-science-ministerial-process/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	Presentation about Polar Research in European Policy at EPB 25 th Anniversary
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (presenter), Anneli Strobel (participant)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Ministerial High-Level & Stakeholder Conference
Name of the event (in English)	All-Atlantic 2021 side event: Networking from pole to pole: facilitating access for research and infrastructure
Date	03/06/2021
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Side event, presentation, chairing
Link to event website if available	https://www.allatlantic2021.eu/ https://www.allatlantic2021.eu/a/networking-from-pole-to-pole-facilitating-access-for-research-and-infrastructure/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	Organisation of side event
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (chair), Anneli Strobel (participant), Renuka Badhe (speaker) Joseph Nolan (organiser), Pjotr Elshout (organiser)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	138
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Conference
Name of the event (in English)	International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences (ICASS X): An Integrated European Research Programme – Opportunities for Social Sciences and Humanities researchers in future EU research projects Session 'An Integrated European Research Programme – Opportunities for Social Sciences and Humanities researchers in future EU research projects'
Date	19/06/2021
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Session organisation, presentation
Link to event website if available	https://icass.uni.edu/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	EU-PolarNet has been tasked in 2015 by the European Commission to co-design an integrated European Polar Research Programme (EPRP) with all relevant polar stakeholders. Over the past five years, the consortium has

	therefore reached out to a wide range of stakeholders through dedicated stakeholder workshops, a Town Hall event, interactive breakout sessions, side events and an online questionnaire and a survey. This has resulted in an EPRP based on the societal challenges and needs, which have been identified through these events and the survey. In this session we would like to present this EPRP. We will especially focus on the opportunities the EPRP will offer SSH researchers. The session will also give some general information about how calls for EU projects within Horizon Europe are normally set up, advise how to set up a consortium and a proposal and how European researchers can cooperate with researchers from non-European countries in these proposals. www.eu-polarnet.eu
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Presentations of Nicole Biebow, Peter Schweitzer and Annette Scheepstra. Renuka Badhe (Chair/moderator), Anneli Strobel (participation)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet sciences White papers and the Integrated EU Polar Research Programme
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	Social scientists and Humanities researchers, 20-30
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Session
Name of the event (in English)	International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences (ICASS X): Co-creation of knowledge and co-design in Arctic research projects: re-thinking calls, seed money and evaluation criteria of funding organisations
Date	19/06/2021
Venue	online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation and organisation
Link to event website if available	https://icass.uni.edu/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	Equity-based research collaboration between Indigenous rights holders and Arctic researchers from the natural sciences, social sciences and humanities has been intensely debated. As a result, ethics and research principles have been developed, but extensive implementation is still lacking. Funding organisations play a crucial role in steering Arctic research into an inclusive direction through setting the terms for the implementation of co-creation and co-design principles in Arctic research. This session aims to discuss how funding agencies can better support the co-creation of Arctic research projects by asking these questions: How can formulation of calls foster co-creation? What are suitable criteria for evaluating this approach in applications? Do we need specific means to support this process, e.g. providing seed-funding for jointly designed applications? This session invites funding organisations, evaluators, Indigenous rights holders and researchers to discuss feasible models for fostering co-creation of knowledge in the Arctic.
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Session organised by (among others) Annette Scheepstra, Gertrude Saxinger, Renuka Badhe (also moderator)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	EU-PolarNet sciences White papers and the Integrated EU Polar Research Programme
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	Social scientists and Humanities researchers about 40 participants
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Meeting
Name of the event (in English)	ESA Polar Science Cluster 2021
Date	15-17/09/2021
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation
Link to event website if available	https://eo4society.esa.int/event/polar-science-cluster-2021/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (presentation), Elaina Ford (presentation), Anneli Strobel (attending)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	<p>N. Biebow explaining the ambition of EU-PolarNet 2</p>
Type and size of audience	EU Polar Cluster, ESA Polar Science Cluster projects, approx. 70
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Presentation
Name of the event (in English)	EU H2020 project CHARTER General Assembly, Helsinki & Online (hybrid)
Date	05/10/2021
Venue	online zoom
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	online oral presentation with slides
Link to event website if available	http://www.charter-arctic.org/first-charter-general-assembly-approaches/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	sharing information about EU-PolarNet and EU Polar Cluster, also on stakeholder involvement, creating synergies
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Kirsi Latola, WP 2 leader of EU-PolarNet 2
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	-
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	NA
Type and size of audience	CHARTER project partners, 40 on site in Helsinki, 20 online
Other relevant information	

6.2 Details about Webinars

Type of activity	Webinar
Name of the event (in English)	EU Polar Cluster meeting in COVID-19 impacts for the cluster projects
Date	15/01/2021
Venue	Online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation
Link to event website if available	
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	Part of the EU-PolarNet 2 Thematic Webinars series
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Pjotr Elshout (organiser), Nicole Biebow (participant), Anneli Strobel (presenter)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	EU Polar Cluster project manager/coordinators, EASME, about 40
Other relevant information	

Type of activity	Webinar
Name of the event (in English)	European Perspectives on the Arctic Science Ministerial Process
Date	28/04/2021
Venue	online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentations, discussions, Q&A
Link to event website if available	https://eu-polarnet.eu/webinar-european-perspectives-on-the-arctic-science-ministerial-process/
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	This webinar aims to explore a European perspective on the ASM process, including underlining developments since ASM2 and contributions to ASM3. The webinar will further explore how existing structures and entities for coordination of polar research in Europe help to facilitate the activities working towards the aims of ASM, nurturing a strong and cohesive European community for Arctic research.
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Renuka Badhe (opening talk, chair), Nicole Biebow (presenter)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	

Type and size of audience	
Other relevant information	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p4_f4uHBK2A&t=12s

Type of activity	Webinar
Name of the event (in English)	How to apply for an EU PolarNet 2 Service Contract?
Date	08/07/2021
Venue	online
Dissemination Type (Poster, exhibition, presentation etc.)	Presentation
Link to event website if available	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_gdh7rqnw5c
Relevance/objective of the participation in scope of the EU-PolarNet 2 project	The webinar demonstrated the background of the Calls, i.e. the European Polar Research Programme, the requirements for the application and how to prepare a valid application for the EU-PolarNet 2 Service Contracts.
EU-PolarNet 2 Participants at the event and their role	Nicole Biebow (presenter), Anneli Strobel (presenter)
EU-PolarNet 2 materials displayed/distributed	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_gdh7rqnw5c
Images (Annex images and include credit information)	
Type and size of audience	48
Other relevant information	

6.3 Webpage

6.3.1 Webpage structure

On the website Home Page, the visitors encounter a menu which can lead to the main topics cover inside the website. A brief description of the content present inside each tab will be presented below:

- ⇒ “About” - visitors can select a group of subtopics which lead to the presentation of the objectives and partners of the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium and the history of the EU-PolarNet 1;
- ⇒ “Thematic Activities” – visitors can find a summary of the Work Packages with the identification of the leaders and main tasks framed by a short presentation;
- ⇒ “Achievements” – visitors can see and download the public deliverables from the EU-PolarNet 1 and 2, organise by Work Package;

- ⇒ “Communication” – in this tab, visitors can download the Publications from the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium;
- ⇒ “News” – in this tab it is possible to select a webpage in each the latest news were presented briefly, giving the possibility of opening for a more complete reading. Moreover, through the “News” tab it is also possible to enter on the “Newsletter” page where it will be always displayed the last version sent for the subscribers. In this page, visitors can sign up for the newsletter and visualise the old versions sent;
- ⇒ “Events” – visitors can see a selection of the future events with special interest for the EU-PolarNet 2 community;
- ⇒ Website footer – visitors can obtain information concerning the contact details together with the information about the project funding and with the active icons which allows to open the social media pages associated with the EU-PolarNet 2. On the bottom of the footer, are also present the active words “Privacy Police”, “Terms & Conditions”, “Disclaimer”, “Cookie Policy” which allows to open the referring pages where technical information regarding the functioning of the website is made available.

6.3.2 Webpage statistic

From January to September, the webpage had a total of 5721 visitors. The months with higher activity were May (663 visitors) and July (635 visitors).

On average, the visits to the website had a duration of 2 min. An exception is the time spent on average during January and February which was longer with an average around 6 min. We should consider that this period corresponds to the start of the website.

Most of the visitors (54%) have reached the website directly with the url and 14% through the search engines. Only 6% came from other websites and 3% from the social media.

From the 54% that reached the website directly, 23% were bounce out.

Regarding the origin of the visitors, 12% (673) reach the website from Germany, 12% (669) from United States, 10% (569) from Norway and 6% (347/325) from Portugal and from the Netherlands.

The average time spent on the website, is more pronounced in Portugal since it is from this location that the management is conducted. However, other countries such as Mexico and Columbia were highlighted with a high average time spent on the website close to 15 min.

In what concerns to the bounce phenomenon, the highest percentages (> 70%) were recorded on the African countries, on the United States and in China.

Moving to the activity inside the website, the homepage was the one with the higher number of pageviews (4128) followed by the “Call of Services” page (1294) and by the “About” page (1116).

Label	Visits	Pageviews
/index	3156	4128
call	1111	1294
about	752	1116
newsletter	479	593
work-packages	447	632
publications	354	460
news-2	340	414

6.4 Folder

Our Ambitions

Image: Justin Pohl

To establish a sustainable and inclusive coordination platform to co-develop and advance European polar research.

Image: Kristin Biebow

To support policy-making processes by providing evidence-based advice.

Image: Michiel Munoz

To sustain the coordination platform in a permanent European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO).

Consortium

The EU-PolarNet 2 consortium consists of 25 partners representing all European and associated countries with Polar research programmes and activities. This enables EU-PolarNet 2 to significantly improve the coordination and co-design of European polar research actions. It also provides evidence-based advice for policy-making processes on behalf of the whole European polar community.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003766.

EU-PolarNet2 coordinates the EU Polar Cluster, a network of EU-funded polar projects.

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Cover image: AWI/Stefanie Arndt

Coordinating and Co-designing the European Polar Research Area

Our Goals

- Advance European and International polar research coordination across all disciplines
- Support the development of transdisciplinary and transnational polar research
- Provide strategies for meaningful stake- and rightsholder involvement
- Interact with national funding agencies to develop synergies and optimise the use of resources
- Provide evidence-based policy advice to decision makers
- Support the implementation of sustained observation systems in the Arctic and Antarctic
- Create a permanent European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO)

EU-PolarNet 2 is a coordination platform for co-developing strategies for European Polar Research and its contribution to policy-making.

www.eu-polarnet.eu

Scan the QR-Code to get more detailed information.

Thematic Activities

1. Research Coordination
Lead by: Antonio Quesada (MICINN, Spain)
2. Stakeholder Involvement
Lead by: Kirsi Latola (UOULU, Finland)
3. Research Prioritisation
Lead by: Carlo Barbante (ISP-CNR, Italy)
4. Research Optimisation
Lead by: Jon Børre Ørbæk (RCN, Norway)
5. Policy Advice, Dissemination, Communication
Lead by: Nicole Biebow (AWI, Germany)
6. European Polar Coordination Office
Lead by: Renuka Badhe (EPB, Netherlands)
7. Project Management
Lead by: Anneli Strobel, Nicole Biebow (AWI, Germany)

Image: Justina Dahl

Image: AWI/Pada Verzone

6.5 Factsheet

At a glance

Title:	Coordinating and co-designing the European Polar Research Area
Instrument:	Coordination and Support Action
EU contribution:	€ 3,299,253.75
Duration:	4 years (01.10.2020 - 30.09.2024)
Project Coordinator:	Biebow, Nicole
Coordinating Organisation:	Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung (AWI)
Website:	www.eu-polarnet.eu

Consortium

- AWI - Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung, Germany
- MICINN - The Ministry of Science and Innovation, Spain
- UOULU - The University of Oulu, Finland
- ISP-CNR - Institute of Polar Sciences - National Research Council of Italy, Italy
- RCN - Research Council of Norway, Norway
- EPB - European Polar Board, The Netherlands
- NWO - Dutch Research Council, The Netherlands
- DAFSHE - Danish Agency for Science and Higher Education, Denmark
- CNRS - National Centre for Scientific Research, France
- UoS-CPS - University of Silesia - Centre for Polar Studies, Poland
- BAI - Bulgarian Antarctic Institute, Bulgaria
- UNIVIE-APRI - University of Vienna - Austrian Polar Research Institute, Austria
- IG-TUT - Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia
- WOC Europe - World Ocean Council Europe, France
- BELSPO - Belgian Federal Science Policy Office, Belgium
- AMAP - Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme Secretariat, Norway
- IGOT-UL - Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning of the University of Lisbon, Portugal
- SPRS - Swedish Polar Research Secretariat, Sweden
- UKRI-BAS - United Kingdom Research and Innovation - British Antarctic Survey, United Kingdom
- ITU - Istanbul Technical University Polar Research Centre, Turkey
- USB - University of South Bohemia - Centre for Polar Ecology, Czech Republic
- RANNIS - Icelandic Centre for Research, Iceland
- FAMRI - Havstovan - Faroe Marine Research Institute, Faroe Islands
- ICR - International Centre for Reindeer Husbandry, Norway
- SPI - Swiss Polar Institute, Switzerland

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003766

Coordinating and Co-designing the European Polar Research Area

Image: Stefan Heimbach

The Challenge

The Polar Regions are sentinels of climate change and human resilience and they are also a proven bastion for international cooperation in research and nature protection. European-funded researchers have made significant contributions to understand the consequences of climate change and the structure and functioning of ecosystems at both Polar Regions, and their global interconnections. The EU contributes to the generation of knowledge that is relevant to society, the economy, the environment and politics. The standardisation, dissemination and coordination of all European Polar research activities play a key role in this.

The Objective

EU-PolarNet 2 will provide a platform to co-develop strategies to advance the European Polar research and its contribution to policy-making processes. Once EU-PolarNet 2 ends, the gained experience, the established network and the tools developed to facilitate better coordination and co-design of Polar research actions will be transferred to and sustained by the European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO).

Anticipated Impact

1. Advanced Polar research cooperation and co-creation of knowledge with all relevant stake- and rightsholders.
2. Improved coordination of national resources and investments in European Polar research to ensure their more synergetic use.
3. Improved policy advice at regional, national and EU level and support of the EU's international commitments with respect to Polar sciences.
4. Improved cooperation with international Polar research programmes to jointly develop large-scale international Polar initiatives.
5. European-wide agreed and prioritised Polar research actions.
6. Strong support to the creation of a European Polar Research Area.

Thematic activities

- Research Coordination**
EU-PolarNet 2 will strengthen the European Polar Research Area by establishing tools and services to sustain a durable Intra-European and international cooperation in Polar Research. EU-PolarNet 2 coordinates the EU Polar Cluster, a growing network of EU-funded Arctic and Antarctic research projects and as such a pre-existing example for improved cooperation.
- Stakeholder Involvement**
EU-PolarNet 2 develops procedures to ensure the co-design of Polar research actions with all relevant stake- and rightsholders. It collects best practises, creates processes and provides strategies for capacity building and continued meaningful stake- and rightsholder involvement and makes these publicly available in an online repository.
- Research Prioritisation**
EU-PolarNet 2 develops strategies to advance European Polar research in an international dimension through stakeholder involvement and co-designing of future research plans. It will further identify and develop globally significant large-scale polar research initiatives.
- Research Optimisation**
EU-PolarNet 2 provides an overview and better understanding of the landscape of Polar research funding in Europe and of the diversity and coordination potential of European Polar research programmes. It stimulates better alignment of the Polar research funding programmes by bringing national operators and funders of Polar research closer together.
- Policy Advice, Dissemination, Communication**
EU-PolarNet 2 provides evidence-based advice to questions related to the Polar Regions from other decision makers at European, national and regional levels. Its Policy Advisory Board, a representative group of European experts on Polar issues, guarantees rapid response and evidence-based advice on pressing Polar scientific and socio-economic issues.
- European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO)**
EU-PolarNet 2 will accelerate the development of a fully integrated Polar observing system by facilitating better coordination of the European Polar observing community and its capacities. Furthermore, it will perform the preparatory work for the implementation of the European Polar Coordination Office as a legacy of EU-PolarNet 2.